

ADSORPTIVE PROPERTIES OF SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART II. ADSORPTION OF POTASSIUM SALTS OF VARIOUS ANIONS.

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The adsorption of about a dozen potassium salts of various anions by an amino-resin has been studied. In similar anions the adsorption decreases with increase in molecular weight. The same order of adsorption has also been observed for homologous series of mono- and dicarboxy fatty acids.

Anti-batic solubility-adsorbability relationship is not the sole determining factor. Consideration has to be paid to the molecular weight of the adsorbate and the possibility of its accommodation in the capillary structure of the adsorbent.

Adams and Holmes (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1935, 54, 17) were the first to study the adsorptive properties of the synthetic resins though S. Sato and Sekine (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1921, 24, 51) had drawn attention to the amphoteric nature of the phenol-formaldehyde resins and Shono (*ibid.*, 1926, 29, 53) had recorded the behaviour of some forty metallic salts which reacted with phenolic resins to give coloured derivatives. Adams and Holmes (*loc. cit.*) allowed the solution under examination to run down a column packed with the resin, and, although difficulties due to channelling made the results more or less qualitative, polyhydric phenol-resins were found to exhibit strong and selective adsorptive properties for a large number of cations and amino-resins were found to be quite efficacious for the removal of anions from solution. The consecutive use of phenolic and amino-resins was suggested to effect complete removal of dissolved salts from solution. In a previous paper Bhatnagar, Kapur and Puri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 679) from a quantitative study of the adsorption of a large number of organic and inorganic acids and bases, concluded that the removal of substances from solution by synthetic resins follows the ordinary laws of adsorption. In the present paper the authors have studied the adsorption of a number of potassium salts of various anions by an amino-resin.

The adsorption of anions on acid-extracted charcoal has been studied by Oden and Langelius (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 311). They found that the order of adsorption for various ions changed with concentration. Thus at 0.01M concentration the order of adsorption was $I' > CrO_4'' > CNS' > Fe(CN)_6''' > Br' > ClO_3' > Cl'$ and at 0.2M concentration $CNS' > I' > ClO_3' > CrO_4'' > Br' > Cl' > Fe(CN)_6'''$. The order $I' > Br' > Cl'$ has

also been confirmed by Schilov and Chepelevetskii (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 123, 248) by use of blood charcoal and activated sugar charcoal.

Beckley and Taylor (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 942) have studied the adsorption of silver salts on silver iodide; Mukerjee and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173) of potassium salts on lead chromate; Dhar and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 35, 144) of sodium and potassium salts on freshly precipitated barium sulphate, sols of aluminium hydroxide and vanadium pentoxide. Though various theories have been put forward to explain the adsorption on considerations of valency, coagulating power and solubility of the salts in water, no successful explanation has so far been given which could explain all the facts. In the present paper the authors have come to the conclusion that though there is a general relation between adsorbability and solubility, consideration should also be paid to the molecular weight of the anion.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The resin was prepared by dissolving two parts of *m*-phenylenediamine in 10 parts of dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) to which 5 parts of 40% solution of formaldehyde were slowly added with constant stirring. A dark chocolate coloured resin was immediately precipitated. It was dried in presence of hydrochloric acid to render it completely insoluble in water. It was then repeatedly washed with hot water to remove all soluble impurities, dried, ground to a fine powder and passed through a 100 mesh sieve. A large sample of the resin was prepared in the above manner and used throughout all studies. Thus variations of the interface were only those existing through the mass of the adsorbent. The resin on ignition left no ash.

It should be mentioned here that all attempts to produce water-insoluble resins by condensation in presence of alkalis failed, a soluble product being obtained in every case.

The adsorption experiments were carried out by weighing exactly 1 g. of the resin in clean, dry, glass bottles of the same size to which 100 c.c. of the solution were pipetted. A blank experiment was carried on side by side. The bottles were shaken for the same length of time and kept for thirty-six hours, at the end of which interval the supernatant liquid was decanted and the amount of the solute determined by usual analytical methods. The blank experiment gave the original concentration (C_0), that with the resin the equilibrium concentration (C_e). The amount of adsorption (x) was determined by difference. Equilibrium concentrations were calculated to moles per litre.

The results for adsorption of various anions are recorded in Tables I, IV and V.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

TABLE I.

	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	$\text{Log } C_e$.	$\text{Log } x$.	% Adsorption.	Solubility (g./100 cc. of water at ∞).
KCl	10.000	9.475	0.525	0.9765	1.7202	5.25	34.0
	9.028	8.511	0.517	0.9300	1.7235	5.73	
	8.007	7.500	0.507	0.8751	1.7050	6.33	
	7.000	6.503	0.497	0.8131	1.6964	7.10	
KBr	10.000	9.654	0.346	0.9847	1.5391	3.46	65.2
	8.941	8.610	0.331	0.9350	1.5198	3.81	
	7.940	7.624	0.316	0.8822	1.4997	3.98	
	7.000	6.700	0.300	0.8261	1.4771	4.29	
KI	10.000	9.582	0.318	0.9860	1.5024	3.18	144.0
	9.000	8.686	0.314	0.9388	1.4969	3.49	
	8.000	7.704	0.296	0.8867	1.4713	3.70	
	7.034	6.750	0.284	0.8293	1.4533	4.04	

The adsorption curves are traced graphically and shown in Figs. 1-5. If we consider the various simple halogen salts (Table I), it appears

FIG. 1.

Adsorption of simple anions by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of the aq. soln.

clearly that, with anions of increasing atomic weight, a marked decrease in the adsorbed quantity is obtained. This order is exactly reverse to that

FIG 2.

Sorption of monocarboxy fatty acids by 1 g. of the resin from 100 c.c. of the aq. soln.

obtained by Oden and Langelius (*loc. cit.*) and others on charcoal who found that $I' > Br' > Cl'$. This is as was to be expected, for we have found that in basic resins the normal Traube's rule is also reversed for a homologous series of fatty acids. The results for the adsorption of mono- and dicarboxy fatty acids are given in Tables II and III. It will be seen that the order of adsorption: formic > acetic > butyric and oxalic > malonic > succinic > adipic shows that the adsorption decreases with the increase in molecular weight, which is quite in line with the results obtained in the case of similar anions.

TABLE II.

Monocarboxy fatty acids.

Sorption by 1 g. of the resin from 100 c.c. of aqueous solution of acids.

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	$\text{Log } C_e$.	$\text{Log } x$.	% Sorption.
Formic	10.050	5.981	4.069	0.7768	0.6095	49.47
	9.346	5.320	4.026	0.7259	0.6048	43.00
	8.223	4.299	3.924	0.6334	0.5937	47.73
	7.476	3.645	3.831	0.5617	0.5833	51.25
Acetic	10.090	6.354	3.736	0.8031	0.5724	37.04
	9.030	5.467	3.563	0.7378	0.5518	39.45
	8.037	4.673	3.364	0.6696	0.5268	41.85
	7.010	3.832	3.178	0.5834	0.5022	45.33
Butyric	10.000	7.196	2.804	0.8571	0.4478	28.04
	8.738	6.120	2.618	0.7868	0.4179	30.00
	7.943	5.467	2.476	0.7378	0.3938	31.17
	7.010	4.673	2.337	0.6696	0.3687	33.33

TABLE III.

Dicarboxy fatty acids

Sorption by 1 g. of the resin from 100 c.c. of the aqueous solution of acids.

Acid.	C_o .	C_e .	x .	$\text{Log } C_e$.	$\text{Log } x$.	% Sorption.
Oxalic	9'9060	1'1215	8'7845	0'0498	0'9437	88'68
	8'9730	0'9346	8'0384	$\bar{1}$ '9706	0'9051	89'58
	7'8500	0'7476	7'1024	$\bar{1}$ '8737	0'8515	90'48
	7 0100	0'6074	6'4026	$\bar{1}$ '7835	0'8069	91'33
Malonic	10'090	1'402	8'688	0'1467	0'9389	86'11
	8'925	1'028	7'897	0'0120	0'8975	88'48
	8'409	0'8879	7'5211	$\bar{1}$ '9483	0'8763	89'44
	7'523	0'6541	6'8689	$\bar{1}$ '8157	0'8369	91'30
Succinic	11'400	2'990	8'410	0'4757	0'9248	73'77
	9'438	2'336	7'102	0'3685	0'8514	75'25
	8'223	1'865	6'358	0'2716	0'8033	77'27
	7'290	1'588	5'702	0'2010	0'7561	78'20
Adipic	10'230	3'083	7'147	0'4891	0'8541	70'14
	9'159	2'523	6'636	0'4020	0'8219	72'45
	8'178	2'055	6'123	0'3130	0'7870	74'86
	7'296	1'682	5'608	0'2259	0'7488	76'92

Further, it is interesting to note from Table I that the order of adsorption is exactly the reverse order of the solubilities of the salts in water. This result is confirmed by the observations of Beckley and Taylor (*loc. cit.*) and Mukhrjee and Ray (*loc. cit.*) who have also found that in general the less soluble salts are sorbed more than the soluble ones.

Coming to the monovalent complex anions (Table IV) we see that the inverse solubility-adsorption relation does not hold in quite an exact manner.

TABLE IV.

	C_0	C_e	x	$\text{Log } C_e$	$\text{Log } x$	% Adsorption	Solubility (g / 100 c.c. of water at 20°.)
KClO ₃	12'600	9'300	3'300	0'9685	0'5185	26'19	7'4
	9'150	6'525	2'625	0'8145	0'4149	28'69	
	7'725	5'400	2'325	0'7324	0'3664	30'97	
	6'000	4'050	1'950	0'6075	0'2900	32'50	
KBrO ₃	10'000	8'000	2'000	0'9031	0'3010	20'00	6'9
	9'022	7'160	1'862	0'8549	0'2700	20'64	
	8'030	6'310	1'720	0'8000	0'2355	21'42	
	7'270	5'650	1'620	0'7520	0'2095	22'28	
KIO ₃	9'733	8'398	1'335	0'9242	0'1255	13'72	8'13
	9'357	8'067	1'290	0'9067	0'1106	13'79	
	8'400	7'200	1'200	0'8573	0'0792	14'29	
	6'500	5'498	1'010	0'7396	0'0043	15'54	
KMnO ₄	10'000	1'919	8'081	0'2830	0'9075	80'81	6'34
	9'260	1'650	7'610	0'2175	0'8814	82'17	
	8'020	1'250	6'770	0'0969	0'8306	84'40	
	6'616	0'818	5'798	1'9128	0'7633	87'63	
KCNS	10'000	9'745	0'255	0'9888	1'4065	2'55	68'5
	9'000	8'757	0'243	0'9423	1'3856	2'70	
	7'975	7'745	0'230	0'8890	1'3617	2'88	
	6'918	6'700	0'218	0'8261	1'3385	3'15	

It should be noted that while there is a general relation between the solubility and the adsorbability of a solute there are still notable exceptions, *e.g.*, sulphanic acid though less soluble than benzene sulphonic acid is less

FIG. 3.

Sorption of dicarboxy fatty acids by 1 g. of the resin from 100 c.c. of the aq. soln.

FIG. 4.

Sorption of complex monovalent anions by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of the aq. soln.

strongly adsorbed. Thus low solubility alone is not sufficient to determine adsorbability, it being also necessary to consider if the anion can be accommodated in the internal capillary structure of the adsorbent. Sulphanilic acid having greater molecular weight is adsorbed less than benzene sulphonic acid. Similarly in the case of chlorate, bromate, iodate, though bromate is less soluble than the chlorate and should have been expected to be adsorbed more strongly, is adsorbed less owing to its greater atomic

FIG. 5.

Adsorption of complex polyvalent anions by 1 g. of the resin from 100 c.c. of the aq. soln.

weight. This argument receives confirmation from the work of Hahn (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2014) who found that in the case of radioactive elements the anti-batic solubility-adsorbability relationship is not the sole determining factor but it has to be considered if the element can be incorporated in the crystal lattice of the sparingly soluble precipitate.

The abnormally high adsorption of potassium permanganate is explainable on the fact that it reacts chemically with the resin owing to its strong oxidising nature.

TABLE V.

C_0	C_e	x_e	$\text{Log } C_0$	$\text{Log } x_e$	% Adsorption,	Solubility (in g./100 c.c. of water at 20°).
$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$	10.000	6.019	3.981	0.7795	0.6000	39.81
	9.031	5.400	3.631	0.7324	0.5600	40.20
	8.000	4.760	3.341	0.6776	0.5105	40.50
	7.000	4.140	2.860	0.6170	0.4564	40.86

TABLE V (contd.).

K_2CrO_4	10'000	9'000	1'000	0'9542	0'0000	10'00	61'7
	8'965	8'000	0'965	0'9031	$\bar{1}$ '9845	10'76	
	8'000	7'066	0'934	0'8492	$\bar{1}$ '9703	11'68	
	7'000	6'100	0'900	0'7853	$\bar{1}$ '9542	12'85	
$Na_2S_2O_3$	10'000	9'408	0'592	0'9735	$\bar{1}$ '7723	5'92	70'07
	9'501	8'912	0'589	0'9500	$\bar{1}$ '7701	6'20	
	8'160	7'585	0'575	0'8800	$\bar{1}$ '7597	7'04	
	6'930	6'370	0'560	0'8041	$\bar{1}$ '7482	8'08	
$K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$	10'000	8'571	1'429	0'9331	0'1550	14'29	43'0
	8'400	7'071	1'329	0'8495	0'1235	15'82	
	7'810	6'570	1'240	0'8176	0'0934	16'00	
	6'857	5'714	1'143	0'7569	0'0580	16'67	
$K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$	10'450	10'050	0'400	1'0021	$\bar{1}$ '6021	3'83	32'97
	8'772	8'400	0'372	0'9243	$\bar{1}$ '5705	4'25	
	8'040	7'680	0'360	0'8854	$\bar{1}$ '5563	4'45	
	7'350	7'000	0'350	0'8513	$\bar{1}$ '5441	4'76	

Table V shows the adsorption of some bi-, tri- and tetra-valent anions. We have not as yet tried sufficiently large number of anions to draw any generalisation, but from the little that we have, it is obvious that there is no relation between valency and adsorbability. It should be observed, however, that among the bivalent anions Cr_2O_7'' , CrO_4'' , S_2O_3'' , the order of adsorbability is $Cr_2O_7'' > CrO_4'' > S_2O_3''$ which is exactly the reverse of their solubility.

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